

Blazars as neutrinos emitters

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- Neutrinos in a nutshell and neutrino astronomy
- The problem
- Our three approaches: statistical, theoretical, and population-based
- A possible solution: extreme BL Lacertae objects

Neutrinos in a nutshell

- Italian for “little neutral one” (© Enrico Fermi)
- Electrically neutral, weakly interacting elementary subatomic particle
- Tiny mass: $< 1/1,000,000 m_e (= 9 \cdot 10^{-28} \text{ g})$
- Three types: electron (ν_e), muon (ν_μ), and tau (ν_τ)
- Everywhere:
 - ✓ ~ 340 cosmic neutrinos/cm³ in the Universe
[E ~ 0.0002 eV]
 - ✓ $\sim 10^{11}$ solar neutrinos/cm²/s on Earth
[E $\lesssim 0.5$ MeV]
- Probably the second most common particle in the Universe (dark matter?)

Neutrino Astronomy

- Only **two** astronomical neutrino sources known (for sure):
 - ✓ the Sun
 - ✓ SN 1987a

Neutrinos from the primary proton–proton fusion process in the Sun

Borexino Collaboration*

In the core of the Sun, energy is released through sequences of nuclear reactions that convert hydrogen into helium. The primary reaction is thought to be the fusion of two protons with the emission of a low-energy neutrino. These so-called *pp* neutrinos constitute nearly the entirety of the solar neutrino flux, vastly outnumbering those emitted in the reactions that follow. Although solar neutrinos from secondary processes have been observed, proving the nuclear origin of the Sun's energy and contributing to the discovery of neutrino oscillations, those from proton–proton fusion have hitherto eluded direct detection. Here we report spectral observations of *pp* neutrinos, demonstrating that about 99 per cent of the power of the Sun, 3.84×10^{33} ergs per second, is generated by the proton–proton fusion process.

We have known for 75 years that the energy generated by stars comes from the fusion of light nuclei into heavier ones^{1–3}. In the Sun, hydrogen is transformed into helium predominantly via the *pp* cycle^{4,5}, a chain of reactions releasing 26.73 MeV and electron neutrinos ν_e , and summarized as

The cycle begins with the fusion of two protons into a deuteron, which occurs 99.76% of the time⁶ by means of the primary reaction

neutrinos. The measured solar *pp* neutrino flux is $(6.6 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, in good agreement with the prediction of the standard solar model⁹ (SSM) $(5.98 \times (1 \pm 0.006) \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1})$.

The observation of *pp* neutrinos provides us with a direct glimpse at the keystone fusion process that keeps the Sun shining and strongly reinforces our theories on the origin of almost the entirety of the Sun's energy. Their measured flux can also be used to infer the total energy radiated by the Sun, $3.84 \times 10^{33} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. However, because photons produced in the Sun's core take a very long time (at least a hundred thousand years; ref. 21) to reach the surface, neutrino and optical observations in combination provide experimental confirmation that the Sun has been in thermodynamic equilibrium over such a timescale.

Observation of a Neutrino Burst in Coincidence with Supernova 1987A in the Large Magellanic Cloud

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(Received 13 March 1987)

A burst of eight neutrino events preceding the optical detection of the supernova in the Large Magellanic Cloud has been observed in a large underground water Cherenkov detector. The events span an interval of 6 s and have visible energies in the range 20–40 MeV.

$$e + p \rightarrow n + \nu_e$$

Observation of a Neutrino Burst from the Supernova SN1987A

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(Received 10 March 1987)

A neutrino burst was observed in the Kamiokande II detector on 23 February 1987, 7:35:35 UT (± 1 min) during a time interval of 13 sec. The signal consisted of eleven electron events of energy 7.5 to 36 MeV, of which the first two point back to the Large Magellanic Cloud with angles $18 \pm 18^\circ$ and $15^\circ \pm 27^\circ$.

IceCube (2013)

Evidence for High-Energy Extraterrestrial Neutrinos at the IceCube Detector

IceCube Collaboration*

Introduction: Neutrino observations are a unique probe of the universe's highest-energy phenomena: Neutrinos are able to escape from dense astrophysical environments that photons cannot and are unambiguous tracers of cosmic ray acceleration. As protons and nuclei are accelerated, they interact with gas and background light near the source to produce subatomic particles such as charged pions and kaons, which then decay, emitting neutrinos. We report on results of an all-sky search for these neutrinos at energies above 30 TeV in the cubic kilometer Antarctic IceCube observatory between May 2010 and May 2012.

Methods: We have isolated a sample of neutrinos by rejecting background muons from cosmic ray showers in the atmosphere, selecting only those neutrino candidates that are first observed in the detector interior rather than on the detector boundary. This search is primarily sensitive to neutrinos from all directions above 60 TeV, at which the lower-energy background atmospheric neutrinos become rare, with some sensitivity down to energies of 30 TeV. Penetrating muon backgrounds were evaluated using an in-data control sample, with atmospheric neutrino predictions based on theoretical modeling and extrapolation from previous lower-energy measurements.

Results: We observed 28 neutrino candidate events (two previously reported), substantially more than the $10.6^{+5.0}_{-3.6}$ expected from atmospheric backgrounds, and ranging in energy from 30 to 1200 TeV. With the current level of statistics, we did not observe significant clustering of these events in time or space, preventing the identification of their sources at this time.

IceCube

Sept. 29, 2016

P. Padovani – AGN12

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IceCube (2015) [4 years]

High-energy neutrino physics

$$p + \gamma \text{ or } p + p \rightarrow \pi^0, \pi^+, \pi^-$$

$$\pi^0 \longrightarrow 2\gamma$$

$$\pi^+ \longrightarrow \mu^+ + \nu_\mu \longrightarrow e^+ + \nu_e + \bar{\nu}_\mu + \nu_\mu$$

$$\pi^- \longrightarrow \mu^- + \bar{\nu}_\mu \longrightarrow e^- + \bar{\nu}_e + \nu_\mu + \bar{\nu}_\mu$$

1. $p - p$ or $p - \gamma \rightarrow$ photons, electrons, and neutrinos

1. $E_\gamma \approx 2 \times E_\nu$ and $F_\gamma \approx 2 \times F_\nu$

ID	Dep. Energy (TeV)	Observation Time (MJD)	Decl. (deg.)	R.A. (deg.)	Med. Angular Error (deg.)	Event Topology
1	47.6 ^{+6.5} _{-5.4}	55351.3222110	-1.8	35.2	16.3	Shower
2	117 ⁺¹⁵ ₋₁₅	55351.4659612	-28.0	282.6	25.4	Shower
3	78.7 ^{+10.8} _{-8.7}	55451.0707415	-31.2	127.9	≲ 1.4	Track
4	165 ⁺²⁰ ₋₁₅	55477.3930911	-51.2	169.5	7.1	Shower

ICECUBE PRELIMINARY

ID	E_{dep} (TeV)	Time (MJD)	Decl. (deg.)	R.A. (deg.)	Ang. Err. (deg.)	Topology
38	200.5 ^{+16.4} _{-16.4}	56470.11038	13.98	93.34	≲ 1.2	Track
39	101.3 ^{+13.3} _{-11.6}	56480.66179	-17.90	106.17	14.2	Shower
40	157.3 ^{+15.9} _{-16.7}	56501.16410	-48.53	143.92	11.7	Shower
41	87.6 ^{+8.4} _{-10.0}	56603.11169	3.28	66.09	11.1	Shower
42	76.3 ^{+10.3} _{-11.6}	56613.25669	-25.28	42.54	20.7	Shower
43	46.5 ^{+5.9} _{-4.5}	56628.56885	-21.98	206.63	≲ 1.3	Track
44	84.6 ^{+7.4} _{-7.9}	56671.87788	0.04	336.71	≲ 1.2	Track
45	429.9 ^{+57.4} _{-49.1}	56679.20447	-86.25	218.96	≲ 1.2	Track
46	158.0 ^{+15.0} _{-16.6}	56688.07029	22.35	150.47	7.6	Shower
47	74.3 ^{+8.3} _{-7.2}	56704.60011	67.38	209.36	≲ 1.2	Track
48	104.7 ^{+13.5} _{-10.2}	56705.94199	-33.15	213.05	8.1	Shower
49	59.9 ^{+8.3} _{-7.9}	56722.40836	-26.28	203.20	21.8	Shower
50	22.2 ^{+2.3} _{-2.0}	56737.20047	59.30	168.61	8.2	Shower
51	66.2 ^{+6.7} _{-6.1}	56759.21596	53.96	88.61	6.5	Shower
52	158.1 ^{+16.3} _{-18.4}	56763.54481	-53.96	252.84	7.8	Shower
53	27.6 ^{+2.6} _{-2.2}	56767.06630	-37.73	239.02	≲ 1.2	Track
54	54.5 ^{+5.1} _{-6.3}	56769.02960	5.98	170.51	11.6	Shower

Galactic

Sep1

33	300 ⁺⁴⁹ ₋₄₉	56221.0940900	1.0	282.0	10.0	Shower
34	42.1 ^{+6.5} _{-6.3}	56228.6055210	31.3	323.4	42.7	Shower
35	2004 ⁺²³⁶ ₋₂₆₂	56265.1338659	-55.8	208.4	15.9	Shower
36	28.9 ^{+3.0} _{-2.6}	56308.1642711	-3.0	257.7	11.7	Shower
37	30.8 ^{+3.3} _{-3.5}	56390.1887617	20.7	167.3	≲ 1.2	Track

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ID	Dep. Energy (TeV)	Observation Time (MJD)	Decl. (deg.)	R.A. (deg.)	Med. Angular Error (deg.)	Event Topology
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ICECUBE PRELIMINARY

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Sep1

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Neutrino source candidates*

- Extragalactic:
 - ✓ Star forming galaxies (through SNRs)
 - ✓ Active Galactic Nuclei
 - ✓ Blazars
 - ✓ Gamma-ray bursts
- Galactic:
 - ✓ Galactic cosmic rays
 - ✓ Galactic PeV sources (e.g., PWNe, SNRs)
 - ✓ Microquasars
 - ✓ Extended sources (e.g. *Fermi* bubble)

Neutrinos from BL Lacs:
Tavecchio et al. 2014,
Tavecchio & Ghisellini 2015,
Righi, Tavecchio & Guetta 2016

***Ahlers and Halzen (2016)**

Extreme blazars as counterparts of IceCube astrophysical neutrinos

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ABSTRACT

We explore the correlation of γ -ray emitting blazars with IceCube neutrinos by using three very recently completed, and independently built, catalogues and the latest neutrino lists. We introduce a new observable, namely the number of neutrino events with at least one γ -ray counterpart, N_ν . In all three catalogues we consistently observe a positive fluctuation of N_ν with respect to the mean random expectation at a significance level of 0.4–1.3 per cent. This applies only to extreme blazars, namely strong, very high energy γ -ray sources of the high energy peaked type, and implies a model-independent fraction of the current IceCube signal ~ 10 –20 per cent. An investigation of the hybrid photon – neutrino spectral energy distributions of the most likely candidates reveals a set of ≈ 5 such sources, which could be linked to the corresponding IceCube neutrinos. Other types of blazars, when testable, give null correlation results. Although we could not perform a similar correlation study for Galactic sources, we have also identified two (further) strong Galactic γ -ray sources as most probable counterparts of IceCube neutrinos through their hybrid spectral energy distributions. We have reasons to believe that our blazar results are not constrained by the γ -ray samples but by the neutrino statistics, which means that the detection of more astrophysical neutrinos could turn this first hint into a discovery.

Key words: neutrinos – radiation mechanisms: non-thermal – pulsars: general – BL Lacertae objects: general – gamma-rays: galaxies.

Looking for the “right” sources

- PeV neutrinos \rightarrow protons with $E \approx 10 - 100$ PeV
- pp and $p\gamma$ collisions $\rightarrow E_\gamma \approx 2 \times E_\nu$ and $F_\gamma \approx 2 \times F_\nu$
- Look for γ -ray sources!
 - ✓ Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN): e.g. only $< 1\%$ of all known AGN are in the *Fermi* 3FGL catalogue ($E > 100$ MeV)
- $60 \text{ TeV} < E_\nu < 2 \text{ PeV} \rightarrow 120 \text{ TeV} < E_\gamma < 4 \text{ PeV!}$

Extragalactic Background Light

Using the best catalogues

- **Fermi 2FHL** catalogue ($E > 50$ GeV; Ackermann et al. 2016): 360 sources (257 sources with $|b_{\text{II}}| > 10^\circ$, $> 90\%$ blazars)
- **2WHSP** catalogue (2nd Wise High Synchrotron Peaked; Chang, Arsioli, Giommi, PP, A&A, in press):
~ 1,700 *blazars + candidates* ($|b_{\text{II}}| > 10^\circ$);
 $\nu_{\text{peak,synch}} > 10^{15}$ Hz; 35 sources TeV-detected (148 potential: **FoM**), ~ 350 in *Fermi* 3FGL
- **Fermi 3LAC** catalogue ($E > 100$ MeV; Ackermann et al. 2015): 1,444 sources ($|b_{\text{II}}| > 10^\circ$), ~99% blazars

Our neutrino list

- deposited $E \geq 60$ TeV (to reduce background)
 - angular error $\leq 20^\circ$ (to reduce counterparts)
- \rightarrow 30 events + 21 tracks
(angular errors $\sim 0.4^\circ$) =
51 IceCube events

Table 1. Selected list of high-energy neutrinos detected by IceCube.

IceCube ID	Dep. energy (TeV)	νf_ν^a (10^{-11} erg cm^{-2} s^{-1})	RA (2000)	Dec (2000)	Median angular error (deg)	b_{II} (deg)
3	$78.7^{+10.8}_{-8.7}$	$1.4^{+3.3}_{-1.2}$	08 31 36	-31 12 00	≤ 1.4	+5
4	165^{+20}_{-15}	$0.8^{+1.9}_{-0.7}$	11 18 00	-51 12 00	7.1	+9
5	71.4 ± 9.0	$1.3^{+3.0}_{-1.1}$	07 22 24	-00 24 00	≤ 1.2	+7
9	$63.2^{+7.1}_{-8.0}$	$2.1^{+4.7}_{-1.7}$	10 05 12	+33 36 00	16.5	+54
10	$97.2^{+10.4}_{-12.4}$	$1.2^{+2.8}_{-1.0}$	00 20 00	-29 24 00	8.1	-83
11	$88.4^{+12.5}_{-10.7}$	$1.1^{+2.5}_{-0.9}$	10 21 12	-08 54 00	16.7	+39
12	104 ± 13.0	$0.9^{+2.1}_{-0.8}$	19 44 24	-52 48 00	9.8	-29
13	253^{+26}_{-22}	$1.2^{+2.7}_{-1.0}$	04 31 36	+40 18 00	≤ 1.2	-5
14	1041^{+132}_{-144}	$1.1^{+2.6}_{-0.9}$	17 42 24	-27 54 00	13.2	+1
17	200 ± 27	$1.2^{+2.9}_{-1.0}$	16 29 36	+14 30 00	11.6	+38
19	$71.5^{+7.0}_{-7.2}$	$1.3^{+3.0}_{-1.1}$	05 07 36	-59 42 00	9.7	-36
20	1141^{+143}_{-133}	$1.1^{+2.6}_{-0.9}$	02 33 12	-67 12 00	10.7	-47
22	220^{+21}_{-24}	$0.7^{+1.7}_{-0.6}$	19 34 48	-22 06 00	12.1	-19
23	$82.2^{+8.6}_{-8.4}$	$1.5^{+3.5}_{-1.3}$	13 54 48	-13 12 00	≤ 1.9	+47
26	210^{+29}_{-26}	$1.1^{+2.6}_{-0.9}$	09 33 36	+22 42 00	11.8	+45
27	60.2 ± 5.6	$1.8^{+4.0}_{-1.5}$	08 06 48	-12 36 00	6.6	+10
30	129^{+14}_{-12}	$0.8^{+1.9}_{-0.7}$	06 52 48	-82 42 00	8.0	-27
33	385^{+46}_{-49}	$1.4^{+3.2}_{-1.2}$	19 30 00	+07 48 00	13.5	-5
35	2004^{+236}_{-262}	$1.4^{+3.3}_{-1.2}$	13 53 36	-55 48 00	15.9	+6
38	201 ± 16	$1.2^{+2.9}_{-1.0}$	06 13 12	+14 00 00	≤ 1.2	-2
39	101^{+13}_{-12}	$0.9^{+2.0}_{-0.7}$	07 04 48	-17 54 00	14.2	-5
40	157^{+16}_{-17}	$0.8^{+1.8}_{-0.6}$	09 35 36	-48 30 00	11.7	+3
41	$87.6^{+8.4}_{-10.0}$	$1.4^{+3.2}_{-1.2}$	04 24 24	+03 18 00	11.1	-30
44	$84.6^{+7.4}_{-7.9}$	$1.4^{+3.1}_{-1.1}$	22 26 48	+00 00 00	≤ 1.2	-46
45	430^{+57}_{-49}	$0.9^{+2.0}_{-0.7}$	14 36 00	-86 18 00	≤ 1.2	-24
46	158^{+15}_{-17}	$0.8^{+1.8}_{-0.7}$	10 02 00	-22 24 00	7.6	+26
47	$74.3^{+8.3}_{-7.2}$	$1.6^{+3.8}_{-1.4}$	13 57 36	+67 24 00	≤ 1.2	+48
48	105^{+14}_{-10}	$0.9^{+2.1}_{-0.8}$	14 12 24	-33 12 00	8.1	+27
51	$66.2^{+6.7}_{-6.1}$	$2.2^{+5.0}_{-1.8}$	05 54 24	+54 00 00	6.5	+14
52	158^{+16}_{-18}	$0.8^{+1.8}_{-0.7}$	16 51 12	-54 00 00	7.8	-6
	2600 ± 300		07 21 22	+11 28 48	0.27	+12

Statistical analysis

- N_ν : neutrino events with at least one γ -ray counterpart
- $N_\nu(f_\gamma)$ or $N_\nu(\text{FoM})$
- Chance probability determined on $10^5 - 10^6$ randomised samples
- Results: p-value vs. f_γ or FoM

Statistical analysis

Results: 2FHL

“real” counterparts =
16 - 10.4 ~ 5

0.4%

PP et al. (2016)

Results: 2WHSP

"real" counterparts
~ 5

0.7%

PP et al. (2016)

Results: 3LAC

agrees with
Glüsenkamp et
al. 2015 (2LAC:
no signal, max.
blazar contrib.
< 20%)

"real" counterparts
~ 5

1.3%

PP et al. (2016)

37 HBL matched to 18 IceCube neutrinos (two doubles)

ID	2WHSP name	2FHL name	Common name	offset (deg)	z	FoM	flux ^a	Comments
9	J091037.0+332924	J0910.4+3327	Ton 1015	11.4	0.350	2.0	0.283	positional match (PR14)
	J091552.4+293324	J0915.9+2931	B2 0912+29	11.2	>0.19	2.5	0.324	positional match (PR14)
	J101504.1+492600	J1015.0+4926	1ES 1011+496	15.9	0.212	4.0	1.62	most probable match (PR14)
	J110427.3+381231	J1104.4+3812	MKN 421	12.8	0.031	57.5	12.4	most probable match (PR14)
10	J235907.8-303740		H 2356-309	4.7	0.165	2.0	0.69 ^b	most probable match (PR14)
11	J095302.7-084018	J0952.9-0841	1RXS J095303.4-084003	7.0	-	0.8	0.385	positional match (PR14)
	J102243.7-011302	J1022.7-0112	1RXS J102244.2-011257	7.7	>0.36	1.3	0.171	positional match (PR14)
	J102658.5-174858	J1027.0-1749	1RXS J102658.5-174905	9.0	0.267	1.0	0.196	most probable match?
12	J193656.1-471950	J1936.9-4721	PMN J1936-4719	5.6	0.265	1.3	0.240	most probable match? ^c
	J195502.8-564028	J1954.9-5641	1RXS J195503.1-56403	4.2	-	1.0	0.127	positional match
	J195945.6-472519	J1959.6-4725	SUMSS J195945-472519	5.9	-	1.0	0.183	positional match
	J200925.3-484953	J2009.4-4849	PKS 2005-489	5.6	0.071	10.0	0.970	positional match (PR14)
14	J171405.4-202752	J1713.9-2027	1RXS J171405.2-202747	9.9	-	1.3	0.275	most probable match?
17	J155543.0+111124	J1555.7+1111	PG 1553+113	8.9	-	7.9	4.20	most probable match (PR14)
19	J050657.8-543503	J0506.9-5434	1RXS J050656.8-543456	5.1	>0.26	1.0	0.131	positional match (PR14)
	J054357.2-553207	J0543.9-5533	1RXS J054357.3-553206	6.4	-	2.5	0.527	positional match ^d
20	J014347.3-584551	J0143.8-5847	SUMSS J014347-584550	10.1	-	2.0	0.161	positional match ^e
	J035257.4-683117	J0352.7-6831	PKS 0352-686	7.6	0.087	2.0	0.228	positional match (PR14)
22	J191744.8-192131	J1917.7-1921	1H1914-194	4.8	0.137	1.6	0.814	most probable match (PR14)
		J1921.9-1607	PMN J1921-1607	6.7	-	-	0.397	most probable match?(PR14) ^f
	J195814.9-301111	J1958.3-3011	1RXS J195815.6-30111	9.7	0.119	1.3	0.282	most probable match?(PR14) ^f
26	J090534.9+135806	J0905.7+1359	MG1 J090534+1358	10.9	-	1.0	0.192	positional match (PR14)
	J091552.4+293324 ^g	J0915.9+2931	B2 0912+29	7.9	>0.19	2.5	0.324	positional match (PR14)
27	J081627.2-131152	J0816.3-1311	PMN J0816-1311	2.4	-	2.5	0.344	positional match ^e
35	J130421.0-435310	J1304.5-4353	1RXS 130421.2-435308	14.3	-	2.0	0.235	positional match (PR14)
	J130737.9-425938	J1307.6-4259	1RXS 130737.8-425940	14.8	-	3.2	0.351	positional match (PR14)
	J131503.3-423649	J1315.0-4238	1ES 1312-423	14.6	0.105	2.5	0.157	positional match (PR14)
	J132840.6-472749	J1328.6-4728	1WGA J1328.6-4727	9.2	-	0.4	0.209	positional match
	J134441.7-451007		SUMSS J134441-451002	10.7	-	1.0		positional match
39		J0622.4-2604	PMN J0622-2605	12.8	0.414	-	0.258	positional match
	J063059.5-240646	J0631.0-2406	1RXS J063059.7-240636	10.0	-	1.6	0.322	positional match
	J064933.6-313920	J0649.6-3139	1RXS J064933.8-31391	14.2	-	0.8	0.225	most probable match?
40	J102356.1-433601		SUMSS J102356-433600	9.7	-	2.5	2.08 ^b	most probable match?
41	J041652.4+010523	J0416.9+0105	1ES 0414+009	2.9	0.287	3.2	0.269	most probable match
46	J094709.5-254100		1RXS J094709.2-254056	4.7	-	1.0		positional match
	J102658.5-174858 ^h	J1027.0-1749	1RXS J102658.5-174905	7.4	0.267	1.0	0.196	most probable match?
48	J144037.8-384655	J1440.7-3847	1RXS J144037.4-38465	8.0	-	1.3	0.184	positional match
Se 51	J054030.0+582338	J0540.5+5822	GB6 J0540+5823	4.8	-	1.6	0.187	positional match
	J060200.4+531600	J0601.9+5317	GB6 J0601+5315	1.3	-	1.0	0.101	positional match

Notes. ^af (E > 50 GeV) in units of 10⁻¹⁰ ph cm⁻² s⁻¹.

“Hybrid” SED: MKN 421

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“Hybrid” SED: PKS 2005-489

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Table 2. 2FHL HBL sources with $F(>50\text{ GeV}) \geq 1.8 \times 10^{-11}$ photon $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 2WHSP sources with FoM ≥ 1.0 in one median angular error radius around the positions of the IceCube events. The counterparts of the most probable matches are indicated in boldface.

ID	2WHSP name	2FHL name	Common name	offset (deg)	z	FoM	flux ^a	Comments
9	J091037.0+332924	J0910.4+3327	Ton 1015	11.4	0.350	2.0	0.283	positional match (PR14)
	J091552.4+293324	J0915.9+2931	B2 0912+29	11.2	>0.19	2.5	0.324	positional match (PR14)
	J101504.1+492600	J1015.0+4926	1ES 1011+496	15.9	0.212	4.0	1.62	most probable match (PR14)
	J110427.3+381231	J1104.4+3812	MKN 421	12.8	0.031	57.5	12.4	most probable match (PR14)
10	J235907.8-303740		H 2356-309	4.7	0.165	2.0	0.69 ^b	most probable match (PR14)
11	J095302.7-084018	J0952.9-0841	1RXS J095303.4-084003	7.0	-	0.8	0.385	positional match (PR14)
	J102243.7-011302	J1022.7-0112	1RXS J102244.2-011257	7.7	>0.36	1.3	0.171	positional match (PR14)
	J102658.5-174858	J1027.0-1749	1RXS J102658.5-174905	9.0	0.267	1.0	0.196	most probable match?
12	J193656.1-471950	J1936.9-4721	PMN J1936-4719	5.6	0.265	1.3	0.240	most probable match? ^c
	J195502.8-564028	J1954.9-5641	1RXS J195503.1-56403	4.2	-	1.0	0.127	positional match
	J195945.6-472519	J1959.6-4725	SUMSS J195945-472519	5.9	-	1.0	0.183	positional match
	J200925.3-484953	J2009.4-4849	PKS 2005-489	5.6	0.071	10.0	0.970	positional match (PR14)
14	J171405.4-202752	J1713.9-2027	1RXS J171405.2-202747	9.9	-	1.3	0.275	most probable match?
17	J155543.0+111124	J1555.7+1111	PG 1553+113	8.9	-	7.9	4.20	most probable match (PR14)
19	J050657.8-543503	J0506.9-5434	1RXS J050656.8-543456	5.1	>0.26	1.0	0.131	positional match (PR14)
	J054357.2-553207	J0543.9-5533	1RXS J054357.3-553206	6.4	-	2.5	0.527	positional match ^d
20	J014347.3-584551	J0143.8-5847	SUMSS J014347-584550	10.1	-	2.0	0.161	positional match ^e
	J035257.4-683117	J0352.7-6831	PKS 0352-686	7.6	0.087	2.0	0.228	positional match (PR14)
22	J191744.8-192131	J1917.7-1921	1H1914-194	4.8	0.137	1.6	0.814	most probable match (PR14)
		J1921.9-1607	PMN J1921-1607	6.7	-	-	0.397	most probable match?(PR14) ^f
	J195814.9-301111	J1958.3-3011	1RXS J195815.6-30111	9.7	0.119	1.3	0.282	most probable match?(PR14) ^f

≈ 5 “most probable” matches (plus ≈ 5 possible ones)

out of 51 IceCube neutrinos →

39	J0622.4-2609	J0622.4-2609	PMN J0622-2605	2.8	0.414	-	0.258	positional match
	J063059.5-240646	J0631.0-2406	1RXS J063057.7-240656	10.0	-	1.6	0.322	positional match
	J064933.6-313920	J0649.6-3139	1RXS J064933.8-31391	14.2	-	0.8	0.225	most probable match?
40	J102356.1-433601		SUMSS J102356-433600	9.7	-	2.5	2.08 ^b	most probable match?
41	J041652.4+010523	J0416.9+0105	1ES 0414+009	2.9	0.287	3.2	0.269	most probable match
46	J094709.5-254100		1RXS J094709.2-254056	4.7	-	1.0		positional match
	J102658.5-174858 ^h	J1027.0-1749	1RXS J102658.5-174905	7.4	0.267	1.0	0.196	most probable match?
48	J144037.8-384655	J1440.7-3847	1RXS J144037.4-38465	8.0	-	1.3	0.184	positional match
51	J054030.0+582338	J0540.5+5822	GB6 J0540+5823	4.8	-	1.6	0.187	positional match
	J060200.4+531600	J0601.9+5317	GB6 J0601+5315	1.3	-	1.0	0.101	positional match

Se

PP et al. (2016)

Notes. ^af (E > 50 GeV) in units of 10^{-10} ph $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Photohadronic origin of γ -ray BL Lac emission: implications for IceCube neutrinos

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ABSTRACT

The recent IceCube discovery of 0.1–1 PeV neutrinos of astrophysical origin opens up a new era for high-energy astrophysics. Although there are various astrophysical candidate sources, a firm association of the detected neutrinos with one (or more) of them is still lacking. A recent analysis of plausible astrophysical counterparts within the error circles of IceCube events showed that likely counterparts for nine of the IceCube neutrinos include mostly BL Lacs, among which Mrk 421. Motivated by this result and a previous independent analysis on the neutrino emission from Mrk 421, we test the BL Lac–neutrino connection in the context of a specific theoretical model for BL Lac emission. We model the spectral energy distribution (SED) of the BL Lacs selected as counterparts of the IceCube neutrinos using a one-zone lepto-hadronic model and mostly nearly simultaneous data. The neutrino flux for each BL Lac is self-consistently calculated, using photon and proton distributions specifically derived for every individual source. We find that the SEDs of the sample, although different in shape and flux, are all well fitted by the model using reasonable parameter values. Moreover, the model-predicted neutrino flux and energy for these sources are of the same order of magnitude

MKN 421

Z 0.031
 $B(G)$ 5
 $R(cm)$ 3×10^{15}
 δ 26.5
 $Y_{\nu\gamma}$ 1.5

Petropoulou et al. (2015)

A simplified view of blazars: the neutrino background

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Can BL Lacs
explain the
neutrino
background?

ABSTRACT

Blazars have been suggested as possible neutrino sources long before the recent IceCube discovery of high-energy neutrinos. We re-examine this possibility within a new framework built upon the *blazar simplified view* and a self-consistent modelling of neutrino emission from individual sources. The former is a recently proposed paradigm that explains the diverse statistical properties of blazars adopting minimal assumptions on blazars' physical and geometrical properties. This view, tested through detailed Monte Carlo simulations, reproduces the main features of radio, X-ray, and γ -ray blazar surveys and also the extragalactic γ -ray background at energies $\gtrsim 10$ GeV. Here, we add a hadronic component for neutrino production and estimate the neutrino emission from BL Lacertae objects as a class, 'calibrated' by fitting the spectral energy distributions of a preselected sample of such objects and their (putative) neutrino spectra. Unlike all previous papers on this topic, the neutrino background is then derived by summing up at a given energy the fluxes of each BL Lac in the simulation, all characterized by their own redshift, synchrotron peak energy, γ -ray flux, etc. Our main result is that BL Lacs as a class can explain the neutrino background seen by IceCube above ~ 0.5 PeV while they only contribute ~ 10 per cent at lower energies, leaving room to some other population(s)/physical mechanism. However, one cannot also exclude the possibility that individual BL Lacs still make a contribution at the ≈ 20 per cent level to the IceCube low-energy events. Our scenario makes specific predictions, which are testable in the next few years.

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Neutrino spectra

$$E_\nu F(E_\nu) \propto Y_{\nu\gamma} \overset{= L_\nu/L_\gamma}{E_\nu^{1-s}} \exp(-E_\nu / E_0) F_\gamma(> 10 \text{ GeV})$$

$$E_0 \cong \frac{17.5 \text{ PeV}}{(1+z)^2} \left(\frac{\delta}{10}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{synch, peak}}}{10^{16} \text{ Hz}}\right)^{-1}$$

We “sum up” the neutrino flux from each individual BL Lac in the simulation to derive the background

The cumulative neutrino emission

No free parameters!

PP et al. (2015)

The big picture

Giommi & PP (2015)

PP et al. (2015)

“Hybrid” SED

Sept. 29, 201

PP et al. (2016)

Summary

- BL Lacs are excellent candidate counterparts of IceCube neutrinos, from the observational/statistical, theoretical, and population point of view. Consistent picture from three different approaches:
 1. Strong, VHE γ -ray HBL (**extreme blazars**) can explain $\approx 10 - 20\%$ of the IceCube signal:
p-value $\gtrsim 0.4\%$
 2. **Lepto-hadronic models** can explain the hybrid SEDs of some HBL
 3. HBL as a class can explain the **high-energy (> 0.5 PeV) part of the IceCube diffuse emission** (and some of the low energy events)

Summary

- A different population/physical mechanism is needed at lower energies (other blazars give null results)
- A few BL Lacs should be at the sensitivity level of IceCube now (or very soon)

Blazars (AGN) could be truly multi-messenger sources

Outlook

- IceCube:
 - ✓ 5th year data: by the end of the year
 - ✓ upper limits will become more and more stringent
 - ✓ searches for deviation from isotropy (Galactic/extra-galactic different component, large scale anisotropies)
 - ✓ stacking for selected catalogues
- Cosmic rays!?

The future

Limited by neutrino statistics → more data from IceCube (and KM3NeT, IceCube-Gen2, etc.) will hopefully turn our **hint** ($\sim 3\sigma$) into a **discovery** ($\sim 5\sigma$)

PP et al. (2016)